

MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA BOLALARGA MIQDOR VA SANOQNI O'RGATISH YO'LLARI

Kazoqov R.T.

O'zDJTSU., Katta o'qituvchi.

Matmurodov A.K.

TVChDPU. O'qituvchi.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13998667>

Annotatsiya. Maktabgacha tarbiya yoshidagi bolalarni o'qitish o'ziga xos xususiyatga ega. Maktabgacha tarbiya yoshida echilishi kerak bo'lgan vazifalar hal qilinmasa, maktabgacha o'qitish muvaffaqiyatli bo'lmaydi.

Kalit so'z: son va sanoq, tarbiyachi, bolalar, maktabgacha tarbiya, o'yin, huddi shunday, bitta va ko'p.

WAYS OF TEACHING QUANTITY AND COUNTING TO CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

Abstract. Education of preschool children has its own characteristics. Preschool education will not be successful if the tasks that need to be solved at the age of preschool education are not solved.

Key word: number and counting, educator, children, preschool education, game, just like that, one and many.

СПОСОБЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ КОЛИЧЕСТВУ И СЧЕТУ ДЕТЕЙ В ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯХ

Аннотация. Обучение детей дошкольного возраста имеет свои особенности. Дошкольное образование не будет успешным, если не будут решены задачи, которые необходимо решить в дошкольном возрасте.

Ключевые слова: число и счет, воспитатель, дети, дошкольное образование, игра, просто так, один и много.

Miqdor va sanoq. Maktabgacha tarbiya yoshidagi bolalarni o'qitish o'ziga xos xususiyatga ega. Maktabgacha tarbiya yoshida echilishi kerak bo'lgan vazifalar hal qilinmasa, maktabgacha o'qitish muvaffaqiyatli bo'lmaydi. Bu vazifalardan biri konkret bilimlar va tafakkur usullaridan abstrakt bilim va usullarga o'tishdan iborat. Bu xil o'tish saviyasi, ayniqsa, matematika o'qitish uchun zarurdir. Bunday savyaning bo'lmasligi yoki etarli bo'lmaligi ikki tomonlama qiyinchilikka olib keladi. Bir tomondan, maktabgacha tarbiya yoshidagi bolalar ko'pincha

maktabga mavhum matematik usullarni egallagan holda keladilar, bularni bartaraf qilish juda qiyin bo'ladi. Ikkinchi tomondan, bolalar maktabda abstrakt bilimlarni egallar ekanlar, ko'pincha ularni formal, asl mazmunini tushunib etmagan holda o'zlashtiradilar.

Shuning uchun ham konsret shart – sharoitlarda matematik usullarni egallagan holda keladilar, bularni bartaraf qilish juda qiyin bo'ladi. Ikkinchi tomondan, bolalar maktabda asbrakt bilimlarni egallar ekanlar, ko'pincha ularni formal, asl mazmunini tushunib etmagan holda o'zlashtiradilar. Shuning uchun ham konkret shart – sharoitlarda matematik bilimlarni qo'llanish imkoniyati juda cheklangan bo'ladi. Shu sababli maktabgacha tarbiya yoshidagi bolalarni o'qitishning muhim vazifasi matematik asbraktlashlar bilan konkret borliq orasidagi bog'lanishni ta'minlaydigan bilim va harakatlarning oraliq saviyasini shakllantirishdan iborat bo'lishi kerak.

Tekshirishlar shuni ko'rsatmoqdaki, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga matematika o'qitishda o'tish saviyasi mazmuni quyidagilardan iborat: Endi har xil guruhlarda “Miqdor va sanoq” bo'limi ustida ishlash uslubiyati haqida fikr yuritimiz. Kichik guruh. Maktabgacha yoshdagi kichik guruh bolalarini sanoqqa o'rgatishdagi bosh vazifalardan biri bir to'plam elementlarini ikkinchi to'plam elementlari bilan taqqoslash, solishtirish yo'li orqali bolalarni to'plamlarni taqqoslashga o'rgatishdan iborat. Bu dastlabki bosqich kelgusida sanoq faoliyatini rivojlantirishda katta ahamiyatga ega. Bola miqdoriy taqqoslash usullarini egallaydi. Bola sanashni bilmaydi, shu sababli u oldin taqqoslanayotgan to'plamlarning qaysinisi ko'p qaysinisi kam ekanini, yoki ular teng quvvatli ekanini aniqlashni o'rganadi.

Bolalarda kelgusida matematik tasavvurlarni rivojlantirish ko'p jihatdan sanoqqa o'rgatishning boshlang'ich davriga bog'liq. Ikkinchi kichik guruhda tarbiyachi bolalarda to'plam alohida bir jinsli elementlar (buyumlar) majmui haqidagi tasavvurni rivojlantirishi kerak.

O'qitishni buyumlarining sifat, xossalarini ajratishga oid mashqlardan boshlash kerak. Masalan, bir qancha o'yinchoqlar ichidan xuddi tarbiyachi qo'lidagidek o'yinchoqni topish taklif qilinadi. “Xuddi shunday o'yinchoqni topish taklif qilinadi. “Xuddi shunday kubchani (bayroqchani, sharni) ber”. Shundan keyin har kubchani (bayroqchani, sharni) ber”. Shunday keyin har xid rangli (o'lchamli, shakldagi) 2-3 ta buyum orasidan xuddi shu rangdagi (o'lchamli, shakldagi) buyumni tanlash topshirig'i beriladi. Navbatdagi bosqich berilgan belgi – alomatlari bo'yicha buyumlarni tanlash va guruhlarga ajratishga, oid mashqlardan iborat bo'lishi kerak.

Masalan: “Qizil rangli hamma kubchalarni mana bu qutiga sol, bu qutiga esa hamma kichik matryoshkalarini yig', mana bunisiga esa hamma katta matryoshkalarini yig'”. Bunday mashqlar natijasida bolalar har xil buyumlarning umumiy belgilari bo'yicha bir guruhga birlashtirish mumkin ekanini tushuna boshlaydilar:

“Bular qo’g’irchoqlar”, “Bular koptoklar”, “Bular bayroqchalar” kabi. Tarbiyachi bolalarni guruhdagi buyumlarning birov qismi uchungina umumiy bo’lgan belgilarni ko’ra olishga o’rgatadi. Masalan, bayroqchalar ko’pligini, ammo ularning ba’zilari sariq, bu’zilari esa ko’k ekanini ko’rsatadi. (Sariq bayroqchalar ko’p, ko’k bayroqchalar ham ko’p). Miqdor haqidagi tasavvurlarni shakllantirishda bir jinsli (bir xil) buyumlardan guruhlar tuzish va guruhni alohida buyumlarga ajratishga doir har xil o’yin – mashqlar ma’lum o’rinni olishi kerak. Odatda bu o’yin – mashqlar ma’lum o’rinini olish kerak. Odatda bu o’yin mashqlar darsda ma’lum izchillikda o’tkaziladi. Birinchi mashg’ulotda bir xil o’lcham va rangli mutlaq aynan o’yinchoqlarning – sabzilar, archalar, jo’ja qancha bo’lsa, o’yinchoqlar ham shuncha bo’lishi kerak. Tarbiyachi dastlab bolalarga bittadan o’yinchoq ulashadi, o’z harakatlarini ushbu so’zlar bilan tushuntiradi:

“Men archalar juda ko’p. Men bolalarning hammasiga bittadan archa berib chiqaman.

Menda bitta ham ham archa qolmaydi...” shunday keyin bolalarga murojaat qiladi “Har biringizda nechtdan archa bor?” Shundan keyin tarbiyachi hamma o’yinchoqni yig’ib oladi, bunda u bitta ham yo’q (bolada) juda ko’p (tarbiyachida) so’zlariga urug’ beradi. Mashqni boshqa o’yinchoqlar bilan yana bir marta takrorlash mumkin. Har gal tarbiyachi ko’p, bitta, bittadan, bitta ham yo’q, hech narsa yo’q so’zlarini ishlatadi; “Qancha?”, “Qanchadan?” – savollarini qo’yadi.

Kichkintoylar buyumlarni va ular qanchadanligini (ko’p, bitta) aytadilar.

Mashg’ulotning borishida bolalar to’plam alohida yuumlarga ajralishiga va alohida buyumlardan tuzilishi mumkinligiga ishonch hosil qiladilar. Ikkinchi mashg’ulot ham shunga o’xshash o’tkaziladi. Dastlab oldingi mashg’ulotda foydalanilgan o’yinchoq turlarining biri bilan ish tashkil qilinadi, keyin esa o’yinchoq yoki buyumlarning yangi xili olinadi, ular bir xil bo’lishi shart emas: ular turlicha o’lchamli va har xil rangli bo’lishi mumkin. O’yinchoqlar guruhlariga ajratiladi, masalan, bir savatga sariq koptoklar, ikkinchi savatga qizil koptoklar yig’iladi; katta baliqchalar katta idishga, kichik baliqchalar kichik idishga solinadi.

Mashg’ulotning borishida tarbiyachi umumlashtiradi. Masalan: “Savatda (yoki to’r xaltada) koptoklar ko’p”, ammo “katta to’r xaltada katta koptoklar ko’p, kichik to’r xalaja kichik koptoklar ko’p” yoki “Ariqda ko’p baliq suzib yuribdi”, yoki “Qizil yoki sariq qayiqchalar ko’p”.

Bu xil mashqlarni kamida to’rt marta o’tkazishdan iborat ekanini bilib olganlaridan keyin; ular bir xil buyumlar guruhlarini mustaqil ajratishni, tevarak – atrofdan alohida (bitta) buyumlarni va buyumlar majmuini (ko’p) mustaqil topishi o’rganadilar. Xonada qanday buyumlar ko’p, qaysi buyumlar bittaligini ayta olish uchun kichkintoylar murakkab fazoviy –miqdoriy tahlilni amalga oshiradilar, ya’ni qandaydir bir buyumni ajratadilar. So’ngra unga diqqat bilan qarab qanday buyumlar bor – yo’qligini qarab, bir xil buyumlarni yagona to’plamga xayolan birlashtirishlari kerak. A.M.Leushina bolalarda buyumlarning miqdoriy tomonlarini abstraktlashtirish va bir xil

buyumlarni yagona to'lamga hayolan birlashtirish malakasini sekin – asta rivojlantirish imkonini beradigan mashqlar tizimini ishlab chiqdi. Kichkintoylarning “Bitta” va “ko’p” tushunchalarini mustahkamlash uchun ko’rsatilgan miqdordagi buyumlarni har xil rangli ikkita qatorga joylashtirishni taklif qilish mumkin. Tarbiyachi quyidagicha topshiriq beradi: “Chapdagi ko’k qatorga bitta jo’ja, o’ngdagi yashil qatorga ko’p jo’ja qo’ying”.

Qatorlarning o’rnini almashtirib yoki har qaysi qatorga joylashtirish kerak bo’lgan buyumlar soni haqidagi ko’rsatmani o’zgartirib, tarbiyachi bolalarni buyumlar miqdorini oldin qatorlar rangi bilan, keyin esa ularning fazoviy joylashuvlari bilan bog’lashni o’rgatadi.

Maktabgacha tarbiya yoshidagi bolalarni o’qitishda matematik bilimlar tarkibini tekshirish tenglik – tengsizlik, qism – butun munosablari, bilvosita tenglashtirish sanoq va arifmetik amallarni to’liq va ongli o’zlashtirish uchun asos bo’ladigan sodda masalalar va munosabatlarning o’zidan iborat ekanini ko’rsatdi. Bu munosabat va masalalarni (ularning eng sodda shakllarini bolalar 3 yoshdan boshlab tushuna boshlaydilar. Ular bunday mashg’ulotlarga katta qiziqish bilan yondashadilar, xuddi shu erning o’zida o’zlashtirganlari (tenglik, qism – butun va h.k. munosabatlari)ni o’yinlarga ko’chiradilar, turmushda seminar ishlar qilishda foydalanadilar, bir – birlariga (katta va tayyorlov guruhi bolalari) shunga o’xshash masalalarni taklif qiladilar.

Maktabgacha tarbiya yoshidagi bolalarning matematik tasavvurlarni o’rganish, tekshirish asosida elementar matematik tasavvurlarni shakllantirish dasturi tuzildi. Bu dastur quyidagi besh bo’limdan iborat: “Miqdor va sanoq”, “Kattalik”, “Geometrik figuralar”, “Fazoda mo’ljol olish”, “Vaqtga nisbatan mo’ljol olish”.

REFERENCES

1. Madraximov S., Madraximova M. ANIQ INTEGRALNI O’QITISHDA GRAFIK ORGANAYZERLARDAN FOYDALANISH //Interpretation and researches. – 2023. – T. 1. – №. 1.
2. Tursunboyeva M. D. KNOWLEDGE FORMS OF CHILDREN'S ORGANIZATION DURING EXPERIENCE WITH NATURE //Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. – 2023. – T. 11. – №. 4. – C. 1029-1032.
3. Abdulkhaevich A. A. et al. INTERDISCIPLINARY INTEGRATION MAINTENANCE EDUCATION AT THE PRIMARY STAGE OF EDUCATION //Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1.5 Pedagogical sciences.

4. Matmurodov A. K. TALABALARGA MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA BOLALARGA MIQDOR VA SANOQNI O'RGATISH YO'LLARI //Экономика и социум. – 2022. – №. 4-2 (95). – С. 256-259.
5. Матмуратов А. К. МЕСТО И РОЛЬ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ В ОБЩЕЙ СИСТЕМЕ ВОСПИТАНИЯ ДЕТЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 9 (88). – С. 528-531.
6. Ачилова М. С. PIRLS КАК СИСТЕМА ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ОСНОВАНИЯ НАВЫКОВ ЧТЕНИЯ В МЛАДШИХ КЛАССОВ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 9 (88). – С. 282-285.
7. Matmurodov A. K. UMUM TA'LIM MAKTABLARI MATEMATIKA FANINI O'QITISHDA AXBOROT TEXNOLOGIYALARNING O'RNI //Научно-практическая конференция. – 2021.
8. Ibragimovna U. T. MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARNING IJODIY FIKRLASH JARAYONLARINI O'STIRISHDA INTERFAOL METODLARDAN FOYDALANISH //ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ. – 2024. – Т. 40. – №. 3. – С. 197-200.
9. Kodirova M. MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTLARIDA HARAKATLI O'YINLARNI TASHKIL QILISH VA TAYYORLOV BOLALARDA AXLOQIY VA IRODAVIY SIFATLARNI SHAKLLANTIRISHDAGI AHAMIYATI //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 12. – С. 198-200.
10. Kodirova M. et al. THE LEVEL OF INFLUENCE OF HYPERACTIVITY ON THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN AND THE IMPORTANCE OF PARENTS //Science and Innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 8. – С. 978-982.
11. Kodirova M. MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM YOSHIDAGI BOLALARDA GIPERAKTIVLIKNING TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA TA'SIR DARAJASI VA OTA-ONALARNING AHAMIYATI //Science and innovation. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. B8. – С. 978-982.
12. Uchqunovna A. L. MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOT TARBIYACHILARIGA AKMEOLOGIK YONDASHISH ASOSIDA TA'LIM BERISH MEKANIZMI //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 35. – №. 1. – С. 61-66.
13. Абдуллаева Л. У. MAKTABGA TAYYORGARLIK GURUHI BOLALARINING O'QUV FAOLIYATIDA O'ZINI NAZORAT QILISHNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING ASOSIY YONDASHISHLARI //Journal of new century innovations. – 2023. – Т. 23. – №. 2. – С. 183-188.

14. Maxmarayimovich S. E. PSYCHOLOGICAL PROPERTIES DEVELOPMENT OF VOLITIONAL QUALITIES IN PUPILS //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2020. – №. 4. – С. 974-981.
15. Umarov D. X. et al. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A SET OF SPECIAL EXERCISES IN ANNUAL PREPARATION TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 742-753.
16. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
17. Turopovich K. R., Rixsibayevna D. S. ENHANCING ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING THROUGH PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES. – 2024.
18. Kazakov R. T. et al. MULTIMEDIA SYSTEMS AND DISTANCE LEARNING TECHNIQUES IN SPORTS SOX //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 99-105.
19. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. МАМЛАКАТИМИЗ ЯНАДА ЮКСАЛИШИДА БОЛАЛАР СПОРТИНИНГ ЎРНИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 5-11.
20. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ПЕДАГОГИКА ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМДА КЕЙС-СТАДИ ТАЪЛИМ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ АСОСИДА ПЕДАГОГИК МАҲОРАТИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ ЮЗАСИДАН ТАЖРИБА-СИНОВ ИШЛАРИНИНГ НАТИЖАЛАРИ //Академические исследования в современной науке. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 111-115.
21. Казоқов Р. Т. Кейс стади технологияларидан фойдаланиб талабаларнинг масофавий таълим технологиялари асосида педагогик маҳоратини шакллантириш //Замонавий футболни ривожлантириш тенденциялари: муаммо ва ечимлари. – Т. 11. – №. 1.
22. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
23. Musaeva U., Mirzaeva U. Дерматоглифические показатели как критерии для прогнозирования уровня развития двигательных качеств у спортсменов с учетом этнических особенностей //Sport ilm-fanining dolzarb muammolari. – 2023. – Т. 1. – №. 3. – С. 110-112.
24. Achilov O. H. TO INCREASE THE INTEREST OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN SPORTS AND TO MAKE THEM REGULARLY ENGAGE IN SPORTS //Educational Research in Universal Sciences. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 218-220.

25. SEIDALIEVA L. D., MUSAEVA U. A., KHAIDAROV T. S. Comparative Assessment of Physical Development and Component Composition of the Body Weight of Sportswoman Participated in Gymnastics //Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies. – 2023. – Т. 17. – С. 87-90.
26. Musaev M. T., Musaeva U. A. JISMONIY FAOLLIK VA UNING INSON SALOMATLIGINI MUSTAHKAMLASHDAGI AHAMIYAT //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2023. – №. 1. – С. 267-273.
27. Safarova D. D., Musaeva U. A., Khushvakova N. Y. ПОКАЗАТЕЛИ ПАЛЬЦЕВОЙ И ЛАДОННОЙ ДЕРМАТОГЛИФИКИ В АСПЕКТЕ ПОЛОВОЙ ИДЕНТИФИКАЦИИ //Academic research in educational sciences. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 1. – С. 326-332.
28. Umarov D. X. et al. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A SET OF SPECIAL EXERCISES IN ANNUAL PREPARATION TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 742-753.
29. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
30. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.
31. Kazoqov R. et al. MARKETING TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ORQALI SPORT TASHKILOTLARI FAOLIYATI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH YOLLARI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 572-578.
32. Aripov Y. Y. et al. PROFESSIONAL SPORTNI BOSHQARISH MODELLARI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 597-587.
33. Jumayev U. X. et al. SPORT SOHASIDA MARKETING FAOLIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRSH //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 588-597.
34. Умаров Д. Х. и др. USE OF NATIONAL-SPIRITUAL VALUES IN EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 455-462.
35. Рахматова Д. Н. и др. EXPERIMENTAL WORK ON THE ORGANIZATION OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK AND ITS RESULTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 447-454.

36. Djalilova S., Tursunboyeva L., Kazakhov R. ENGAGING ENGLISH LANGUAGE LEARNING THROUGH SPORTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 386-395.
37. Tursunboyeva L., Djalilova S., Kazoqov R. ABOUT TEACHING SPEAKING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 376-385.
38. Jumayev U. X. et al. " PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATION INNOVATION CLUSTER" MEANS COMMON GOALS AND SPECIFIC INTERESTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 552-560.
39. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.
40. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
41. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. – 2024.
42. Djurayeva X. X., Xodjiyev R. M., Kazoqov R. T. DIFFICULTIES IN TEACHING RUSSIAN AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 316-326.
43. Beknazarov S. H. Q., Kazoqov R. T. IDEOLOGICAL THREATS AND IMPORTANT PROBLEMS OF IDEOLOGICAL EDUCATION, NATIONAL HISTORICAL THINKING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 1016-1029.
44. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
45. Бойқобиллов А. П. и др. ТУРЛИ МАЛАКАЛИ СПОРТЧИЛАР ТОМОНИДАН ЯДРО УЛОҚТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ТАҲЛИЛЛАРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 30-40.
46. Авезова Г. С., Казоқов Р. Т. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИ МАШҒУЛОТ ЖАРАЁНИДА ҚЎЛЛАНИЛГАН ТИКЛОВЧИ ВОСИТАЛАРНИ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИГА ТАЪСИРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 205-214.
47. Шопулатов А. Н., Казоқов Р. Т., Хайдарова Г. М. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИ ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИГИНИ БАҲОЛАШ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 197-204.

48. Бойқобилов А. П. и др. ТУРЛИ МАЛАКАЛИ СПОРТЧИЛАР ТОМОНИДАН ЯДРО УЛОҚТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ ТАҲЛИЛЛАРИ //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 30-40.
49. Yugay L. P. et al. RECOVERY OF THE BODY OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNING ATHLETES DURING SPORTS TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 365-371.
50. Akbarov A. et al. ANTHROPOMETRIC-PHYSIOLOGICAL INDICATORS OF MIDDLE-DISTANCE RUNNERS AND RECOVERY OF THEIR BODY DURING TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 358-364.
51. Kim D. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PARTICIPATION OF STUDENT ATHLETES IN THE SWEDISH TEAM AND THE SWEDISH TEAM IN THE UZBEKISTAN CHAMPIONSHIP IN HEIGHT ATHLETICS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 346-353.
52. Nurullayeva D. S. et al. ETHICAL PROBLEMS AND THEM IN THE FIELD OF NATURE SOLUTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 480-486.
53. Kazaqov R. T., Djo'rabayev A. M. MEANS OF RECOVERY OF WORKING CAPACITY OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 902-911.
54. Kazoqov R. T., Djo'rabayev A. M. DEVELOPMENT OF CYBER SPORTS IN UZBEKISTAN //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 893-901.
55. Yaqubov F. M. et al. METHODOLOGY OF SELECTION OF 10-12-YEAR-OLD PLAYERS AND ORGANIZATION OF TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 1. – С. 1271-1279.
56. Казоқов Р. Т. ҚИСҚА МАСОФАГА ЮГУРУВЧИЛАРНИНГ ЖИСМОНИЙ ВА МАХСУС ЖИСМОНИЙ ТАЙЁРГАРЛИК КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ //Fan-Sportga. – 2022. – №. 7. – С. 53-55.
57. Гонашвили А. С. и др. Активный досуг узбекской молодежи в аспекте социологического анализа //Теория и практика физической культуры. – 2020. – №. 3. – С. 8-8.
58. Baltayeva I. T. et al. USE OF VIRTUAL LABORATORIES TO CONDUCT FOOTBALL TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 709-718.
59. Baltayeva I. T. et al. CREATING AN INFORMATION-EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT USING MODERN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 700-708.

60. Melziddinov R. A., Akramov B. N., Kazoqov R. T. THE RELATIONSHIP OF THE EFFICIENCY OF TECHNICAL-TACTICAL ACTIONS OF FOOTBALL PLAYERS WITH THE LEVEL OF PHYSICAL PREPARATION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 1153-165.
61. Umarov D. X. et al. NATIONAL MOVEMENT FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS'PHYSICAL PREPARATION USING GAMES //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 732-741.
62. Umarov D. X. et al. THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING A SET OF SPECIAL EXERCISES IN ANNUAL PREPARATION TRAINING OF SHORT-DISTANCE RUNNERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 742-753.
63. Шопулатов А. Н. Бўлажак мураббийларда жисмоний тарбия ва спорт асосида маънавий қадриятларни ривожлантириш йўллари //Фан-Спортга. – 2019. – №. 1. – С. 67-72.
64. Boltayeva I. T., Tashnazarov D. Y., Kazaqov R. T. TECHNICAL-TACTICS OF 13-14-YEAR-OLD FOOTBALL PLAYERS EFFICIENCY OF EDUCATIONAL ACTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 91-98.
65. Boltayeva I. T. et al. ANATOMY OF THE EXACT AND NATURAL SCIENCES TEST TASK //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 6. – С. 99-105.
66. Казоқов Р. Т. и др. ТАЪЛИМ МУАССАСАЛАРИДА ТАРБИЯВИЙ ТАДБИРЛАРДА МИЛЛИЙ-МАЪНАВИЙ ҚАДРИЯТЛАРДАН ФОЙДАЛАНИШ. – 2024.
67. Умаров Д. Х. и др. USE OF NATIONAL-SPIRITUAL VALUES IN EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 455-462.
68. Kazoqov R. T. et al. USE OF NATIONAL-SPIRITUAL VALUES IN EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES IN EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 5. – С. 911-918.
69. Керимов Ф. А. и др. ORGANIZATION OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND FAMILY COOPERATION //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 463-470.
70. Рахматова Д. Н. и др. EXPERIMENTAL WORK ON THE ORGANIZATION OF SPIRITUAL AND EDUCATIONAL WORK AND ITS RESULTS //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 447-454.
71. Beknazarov Z. FUTBOLCHILARNING TEXNIK VA TAKTIK TAYYORGARLIGI //Modern Science and Research. – 2024. – Т. 3. – №. 10. – С. 171-174.

72. Artikov A., Xasanov D. FEATURES OF TEACHING TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL MOVEMENTS OF 13-15-YEAR-OLD GIRLS IN MINI-FOOTBALL AT A COMPREHENSIVE SCHOOL //Modern Science and research. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 335-345.
73. Madaminov J., Artikov A. A STUDY OF THE APPLICATION OF THE" BOUNDED" METHOD IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF QUICK-STRENGTH QUALITIES OF DIFFERENT YOUNG PLAYERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 356-366.
74. Raimkulov A., Artikov A. DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL FITNESS IN TRAINING //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 285-294.
75. Nizomiddinov S., Artikov A. ORGANIZATIONAL ACTIONS OF ATTACKS IN THE GAME OF EUROPEAN FOOTBALL TEAMS //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 345-355.
76. Xasanov D., Artikov A. RESULTS OF INCREASING THE TECHNICAL AND TACTICAL CAPABILITIES OF FOOTBALL TEAMS //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 243-252.
77. Choriyev A., Artiqov A. ANALYSIS OF TEAM TACTICAL GAMES IN THE MODERN FOOTBALL GAME //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 221-231.
78. Sherqulov S., Artiqov A. BASIC REQUIREMENTS FOR MEANINGFUL TRAINING OF YOUNG PLAYERS //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 211-220.
79. Xudiyarov S., Artiqov A. THE IMPORTANCE OF INTERNATIONAL FOOTBALL COMPETITIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF GIRLS'FOOTBALL IN OUR COUNTRY //Modern Science and Research. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 232-242.
80. Artikov A., Abduhamidov J. COMPARISON OF THE RESULTS OF THE PLAYERS DURING THE GAME //Modern Science and Research. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 1. – C. 302-312.